

INCREASING THE PRODUCTIVITY OF WHEAT USING SYNTHETIC PLANT GROWTH REGULATORS METHYUR, KAMETHUR AND IVIN

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Abstract

The regulatory effect of synthetic plant growth regulators Methyur, Kamethur and Ivin on the productivity of spring wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) variety Demira, grown in the field, was studied. The conducted studies showed that the treatment of wheat seeds before planting in the soil with aqueous solutions of plant growth regulators Methyur, Kamethur and Ivin in concentrations from 10^{-4} M to 10^{-7} M increases the yield of wheat. Quantitative indicators of wheat productivity increased: average weight of 10 spikes (g) - by 41.30 - 94.05 %, average spike length (mm) - by 21.33 - 66.28 %, grain yield (kg/0.1ha) - by 5.87 - 20.24 %, respectively, compared to similar indicators of control plants. The highest quantitative indicators of wheat productivity were obtained when wheat seeds were treated before planting in the soil with plant growth regulators in the most effective concentrations: Methyur - 10^{-5} M, 10^{-6} M and 10^{-7} M, Kamethur - 10^{-4} M, 10^{-6} M and 10^{-7} M, Ivin - 10^{-5} M and 10^{-7} M. The conducted studies indicate the prospect of using new environmentally friendly synthetic plant growth regulators Methyur, Kamethur and Ivin to increase wheat productivity.

Keywords: plant growth regulators, Methyur, Kamethur, Ivin, wheat productivity.

Introduction. The development of new environmentally friendly plant growth regulators to increase the productivity of the important grain crop wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) while reducing the use of environmentally toxic agrochemicals is an urgent task of modern agriculture [1, 2]. Abiotic and biotic stress factors such as global climate change, environmental pollution, salinity and soil depletion are key negative factors affecting crop production worldwide [3 - 5].

Today, to solve this urgent problem, natural or synthetic plant growth regulators are used for better assimilation of nutrients, improvement of growth and photosynthetic efficiency of plants, which contributes to increased yield and plant resistance to stress factors [6 - 9]. The use of natural or synthetic plant growth regulators is one of the promising areas of agriculture, which will contribute to improving the quality of products, increasing yield and stress resistance of plants.

Recently, considerable attention has been paid to the development of new environmentally safe plant growth regulators based on synthetic low molecular weight heterocyclic compounds, pyridine and pyrimidine derivatives [10 - 12]. Thanks to the use of plant growth regulators based on synthetic compounds, pyridine and pyrimidine derivatives, it is possible to improve plant growth and development, increase yield and stress resistance. New ecologically safe plant growth regulators based on synthetic compounds, derivatives of N-oxide-2,6-dimethylpyridine (Ivin), 6-

methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine sodium and potassium salts (Methyur and Kamethur) were elaborated and proposed to be used to improve the growth and increase the productivity of grain, leguminous, vegetable and industrial crops [12 - 15]. The use of ecologically safe synthetic plant growth regulators will reduce the consumption of pesticides and fungicides toxic to human and animal health for plant protection [16, 17], improve the balance of natural ecosystems and soils, and the ecological condition of the entire agricultural system [12 - 15].

The aim of this work is to study the regulatory effect of synthetic plant growth regulators Methyur, Kamethur and Ivin on the productivity of spring wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) variety Demira grown in the field.

Materials and methods.

Chemical structures of plant growth regulators. Chemical structures of synthetic plant growth regulators: Ivin (N-oxide-2,6-dimethylpyridine), Methyur (sodium salt of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine) and Kamethur (potassium salt of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine) are presented in Fig. 1. These plant growth regulators were synthesized at the Department for Chemistry of Bioactive Nitrogen-Containing Heterocyclic Compounds, V.P. Kukhar Institute of Bioorganic Chemistry and Petrochemistry of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine.

Figure 1. Chemical structures of synthetic synthetic plant growth regulators: Ivin (*N*-oxide-2,6-dimethylpyridine), MW=125,17; Methyur (sodium salt of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine), MW=165,17; Kamethur (potassium salt of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine, MW=181,28

Cultivation of wheat plants in field conditions.

The study of the effect of synthetic plant growth regulators of Methyur, Kamethur and Ivin on the productivity of spring wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) variety Demira, grown in the field, was carried out. For this purpose, wheat seeds before planting in the soil were treated by spraying with aqueous solutions of plant growth regulators Ivin, Methyur and Kamethur, applied in concentrations from 10^{-4} M to 10^{-7} M. After this procedure, the treated seeds were dried and planted in the soil. Field research was conducted according to the methods given in the manual [18]. The analysis of quantitative indicators of the yield of wheat plants (average weight of 10 spikes (g), average spike length (mm), grain yield (kg/0.1ha)) was carried out according to the methods [18, 19]. Quantitative indicators of yield determined on experimental wheat plants treated with synthetic plant growth regulators compared to similar

indicators of control wheat plants not treated with synthetic plant growth regulators were expressed in (%). Statistical processing of the experimental data, performed in triplicate, was carried out according to the Student's t-test with a significance level of $P \leq 0.05$; mean values \pm standard deviation (\pm SD).

Results and Discussion.

The conducted field studies showed that the pre-sowing treatment of seeds of spring wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) variety Demira with aqueous solutions of synthetic plant growth regulators Methyur, Kamethur and Ivin, applied in the concentration range of 10^{-4} M - 10^{-7} M, increases the quantitative indicators of wheat productivity (Fig. 2 - 5). The average weight of 10 spikes (g) increased - by 41.30 - 94.05 % (Fig. 3), average spike length (mm) - by 21.33 - 66.28 % (Fig. 4), grain yield (kg/0.1ha) - by 5.87 - 20.24 % (Fig. 5), respectively, compared to similar indicators of control plants.

Figure 2. Spikes of spring wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) variety Demira grown from seeds not treated with synthetic plant growth regulators (control plants) or treated with synthetic plant growth regulators Methyur, Kamethur and Ivin (experimental plants), applied in the concentration range of 10^{-4} M - 10^{-7} M

The highest quantitative indicators of wheat productivity were obtained by treating wheat seeds before planting in the soil with the plant growth regulator Methyur in the most effective concentrations: $10^{-5}M$, $10^{-6}M$ and $10^{-7}M$. Pre-sowing treatment of seeds of the spring wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) variety Demira with aqueous solutions of synthetic plant growth regulator Methyur, applied in the concentrations $10^{-5}M$, $10^{-6}M$ and $10^{-7}M$, increases the quantitative indicators of wheat productivity as follows: the average weight of 10 spikes (g) increased - by 57.39 - 94.05 % (Fig. 3), average spike length (mm) - by 21.33 - 66.28 % (Fig. 4), grain yield (kg/0.1ha) - by 9.51 - 20.24 % (Fig. 5), respectively, compared to similar indicators of control plants.

Figure 3. The average weight of 10 spikes (g) of spring wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) variety Demira grown from seeds not treated with synthetic plant growth regulators (control plants) or treated with synthetic plant growth regulators Methyur, Kamethur and Ivin (experimental plants), applied in the concentration range of $10^{-4}M$ - $10^{-7}M$

The highest quantitative indicators of wheat productivity were obtained by treating wheat seeds before planting in the soil with the plant growth regulator Kamethur in the most effective concentrations: $10^{-4}M$, $10^{-6}M$ and $10^{-7}M$. Pre-sowing treatment of seeds of the spring wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) variety Demira with aqueous solutions of synthetic plant growth regulator Kamethur, applied in the concentrations $10^{-4}M$, $10^{-6}M$ and $10^{-7}M$, increases the quantitative indicators of wheat productivity as follows: the average weight of 10 spikes (g) increased - by 54.93 - 82.27 % (Fig. 3), average spike length (mm) - by 27.72 - 59.64 % (Fig. 4), grain yield (kg/0.1ha) - by 5.87 - 18.28 % (Fig. 5), respectively, compared to similar indicators of control plants.

The highest quantitative indicators of wheat productivity were obtained by treating wheat seeds before planting in the soil with the plant growth regulator Ivin in the most effective concentrations: $10^{-5}M$ and $10^{-7}M$. Pre-sowing treatment of seeds of the spring wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) variety Demira with aqueous solutions of synthetic plant growth regulator Ivin, applied in the concentrations $10^{-5}M$ and $10^{-7}M$, increases the quantitative indicators of wheat productivity as follows: the average weight of 10 spikes (g) increased - by 41.30 - 80.18 % (Fig. 3), average spike length (mm) - by 25.59 - 59.64 % (Fig. 4), grain yield (kg/0.1ha) - by 13.45 - 18.47 % (Fig. 5), respectively, compared to similar indicators of control plants.

Figure 4. The average spike length (mm) of spring wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) variety Demira grown from seeds not treated with synthetic plant growth regulators (control plants) or treated with synthetic plant growth regulators Methyur, Kamethur and Ivin (experimental plants), applied in the concentration range of $10^{-4}M$ - $10^{-7}M$

The highest quantitative indicators of wheat productivity were obtained by treating wheat seeds before planting in the soil with the plant growth regulator Ivin in the most effective concentrations: $10^{-5}M$ and $10^{-7}M$. Pre-sowing treatment of seeds of the spring wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) variety Demira with aqueous solutions of synthetic plant growth regulator Ivin, applied in the concentrations $10^{-5}M$ and $10^{-7}M$, increases the quantitative indicators of wheat productivity as follows: the average weight of 10 spikes (g) increased - by 41.30 - 80.18 % (Fig. 3), average spike length (mm) - by 25.59 - 59.64 % (Fig. 4), grain yield (kg/0.1ha) - by 13.45 - 18.47 % (Fig. 5), respectively, compared to similar indicators of control plants.

The highest quantitative indicators of wheat productivity were obtained by treating wheat seeds before planting in the soil with the plant growth regulator Ivin in the most effective concentrations: $10^{-5}M$ and $10^{-7}M$. Pre-sowing treatment of seeds of the spring wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) variety Demira with aqueous solutions of synthetic plant growth regulator Ivin, applied in the concentrations $10^{-5}M$ and $10^{-7}M$, increases the quantitative indicators of wheat productivity as follows: the average weight of 10 spikes (g) increased - by 41.30 - 80.18 % (Fig. 3), average spike length (mm) - by 25.59 - 59.64 % (Fig. 4), grain yield (kg/0.1ha) - by 13.45 - 18.47 % (Fig. 5), respectively, compared to similar indicators of control plants.

Figure 5. The grain yield (kg/0.1ha) of spring wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) variety Demira grown from seeds not treated with synthetic plant growth regulators (control plants) or treated with synthetic plant growth regulators Methyur, Kamethur and Ivin (experimental plants), applied in the concentration range of $10^{-4}M$ - $10^{-7}M$

Based on the obtained results, it should be assumed that the high growth-regulating effect of the synthetic plant growth regulators Methyur (sodium salt of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine), Kamethur (potassium salt of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine) and Ivin (N-oxide-2,6-dimethylpyridine), is explained by their auxin-like and cytokinin-like effects [20] on the proliferation, elongation and differentiation of plant cells, which are the main processes of growth and development of roots, shoots and spikes of wheat plants. Moreover, the chemical composition of these environmentally friendly synthetic plant growth regulators has a positive effect on plant growth, metabolism and adaptation to heavy metals, salt and osmotic stress [12 - 15, 21] due to the presence of macroelements such as nitrogen, potassium, sulfur and sodium (Fig. 1). As a result of these processes, the yield of wheat plants increases.

Conclusion. The obtained results indicate the prospect for the practical use of new environmentally friendly synthetic plant growth regulators Methyur, Kamethur and Ivin, applied in the concentration range of $10^{-4}M$ - $10^{-7}M$, to increase the productivity of spring wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) variety Demira.

Statement of Conflict of Interest.

The authors are declared that they have no conflict with this research article.

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